

Effect of Al, Ti and C additions on Widmanstätten microstructures and mechanical properties of cast $Al_{0.6}CoCrFeNi$ compositionally complex alloys

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Effect of Ti, Al and C additions on microstructure and properties of $Al_{0.6}CoCrFeNi$ alloy.
- The additions of Ti or Ti+C allow to refine the cast microstructure of $Al_{0.6}CoCrFeNi$.
- This microstructural refinement results in superior mechanical properties. At 700 °C, the alloys strongly soften and become more brittle except for those with Ti. These alloys exhibit an excellent ductility due to grain boundary sliding

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

The cast microstructure of the $Al_{0.6}CoCrFeNi$ compositionally complex alloy was successfully refined with small additions of Al, Ti and C and its mechanical properties were optimized. In the as-cast state, this alloy has a Widmanstätten microstructure with coarse grains (~110 μm) of a strong BCC/B2 matrix and soft FCC plates (~65 vol.%) with large widths (~1.3 μm). The addition of 0.25 at.% C to $Al_{0.6}CoCrFeNi$ stabilizes the FCC phase and favors the formation of a coarse dendritic microstructure making this alloy unsuitable for structural applications. In contrast, alloying of either 3 at.% Al, Ti, or 3% Ti and 0.25% C to $Al_{0.6}CoCrFeNi$ refined its Widmanstätten microstructure, i.e. the thickness of the FCC plates and/or the size of the prior BCC/B2 grains were significantly reduced. As a result of these microstructural changes, Al and Ti containing alloys show an outstanding strength (twice higher than that of $Al_{0.6}CoCrFeNi$) and ductilities ≤5% at 20 °C. These properties are retained at 400 °C but at 700 °C, the strength and ductility of almost all alloys decrease. However, Ti containing alloys exhibit much larger ductilities (~50%) at 700 °C due to their high density of grain boundaries which accommodate plastic deformation through grain boundary sliding.

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1. Introduction

During the last decade, high-entropy alloys (HEAs) have attracted increasing interest in the scientific community due to their outstanding mechanical properties [1,2]. To date, most studies in this research field have focused on fundamental aspects of single-phase solid solutions such as model alloys from the FCC CoCrFeMnNi [3–6] and BCC HfNbTaTiZr systems [7–12]. However, it was recognized that these single-phase alloys are unlikely to meet the properties required for engineering applications [13]. Therefore more recent efforts aimed to develop compositionally complex alloys (CCAs) containing multiple phases. For this purpose, a single element was systematically added to known single-phase HEAs to promote the precipitation of intermetallic compounds in the parent matrix. In particular, the addition of Al to various FCC high- and medium-entropy alloys such as CoCrFeMnNi [14], CoCrFeNi [15–17], CoCrNi [18,19], and CuCrFeNi₂ [20,21] has been reported to result in the formation of disordered and ordered FCC and BCC phases which formation depends on alloy composition [17,21] and thermomechanical heat treatments [22–24]. The microstructures and phases in as-cast alloys of the Al_xCoCrFeNi system were found to be very sensitive to the Al concentration, i.e. it varies from a single-phase FCC solid solution for low Al-concentrations ($x < 0.5$), to a multi-phase FCC + BCC/B2 for intermediate Al-contents ($0.5 < x < 0.9$) to two phase BCC/B2 for high concentrations ($0.9 < x < 2.0$) [15,17,25–29]. These transitions are often attributed to the fact that Al atoms are much larger compared to Co, Cr, Fe, and Ni atoms. As a result of the large size misfit of Al, the FCC phase has a limited Al-solubility and the alloy decomposes into FCC and BCC structures for larger Al concentrations [21]. Furthermore, it was shown that the BCC structure decomposes through a spinodal mechanism into an ordered NiAl-rich B2 intermetallic and a disordered FeCr-rich BCC solid solution [30].

Regarding their mechanical properties, the single-phase FCC Al_xCoCrFeNi cast alloys with $x < 0.5$ were reported to be soft and ductile. In contrast, the two-phase BCC/B2 cast alloys for $x > 0.8$ were shown to be very hard with a microhardness of ~ 500 HV [17] and extremely brittle. Interestingly, in a narrow composition range with $0.6 < x < 0.8$, the cast alloys exhibit a fine Widmanstätten microstructure composed of disordered FCC plates in a BCC/B2 matrix [17,25,27,31,32]. This composition range is therefore promising to develop alloys with a good combination of strength and ductility if their processing and relative phase volume fractions are carefully controlled. In such multi-phase alloys such as Al_{0.6}CoCrFeNi and Al_{0.7}CoCrFeNi, the superior mechanical properties were shown to result from the intrinsic properties of the constituent phases as well as their volume fractions and the deformation incompatibilities which occur at phase boundaries [31]. Indeed, Abuzaid et al. [31] showed that the plastic deformation is mostly accommodated by the soft FCC phase where dislocations are piling up against phase boundaries while the BCC and B2 phases remain nearly undeformed at low plastic strains.

As-cast alloys have generally anisotropic and coarse solidification microstructures which require further optimizations to obtain desired mechanical properties. In the as-cast state, the Al_{0.7}CoCrFeNi alloy typically exhibits a coarse Widmanstätten microstructure [31,32] with large prior BCC/B2 grains in which a large volume fraction of FCC lamellae precipitate and grow upon cooling. It is well known in the literature that the strength of such kind of alloy can be significantly improved through a decrease of the lamellar spacing based on a Hall-Petch-type of relationship [33,34].

In the present paper, an effort was made to refine the Widmanstätten microstructure of the as-cast Al_{0.6}CoCrFeNi alloy through small Al, Ti, and C additions. All studied alloys were arc melted in a protective argon atmosphere and subsequently drop

cast in a copper mold. The chemical composition, microstructure and phase volume fractions of the cast alloys were carefully analyzed by XRD, SEM, EDX, EBSD, and TEM. The mechanical properties of the alloys were systematically investigated by microhardness and tensile tests at temperatures between room temperature and 700 °C. Our results show that a significant refinement of the prior BCC/B2 grain size as well as a decrease of the thickness of the FCC lamellae can be obtained through the addition of optimum levels of Ti and C. This microstructural refinement through microalloying results in superior tensile properties.

2. Experimental methods

2.1. Material processing

The CCA ingots were prepared in a high-purity Ar atmosphere by arc melting a mixture of high purity metals Al, Cr, Fe, Co, Ni, Ti (purity >99.9 wt%) and a NiC pre-alloy (97.9 wt% Ni and 2.1 wt% C). Before melting, the chamber containing the raw materials was first evacuated to $\sim 1.5 \times 10^{-2}$ mbar with a rotary pump and subsequently to $\sim 4.0 \times 10^{-5}$ mbar with a turbopump. The vacuumed chamber was then backfilled with pure Ar. This process was repeated 3 times. After the final backfilling, the chamber pressure was ~ 700 mbar. A small piece of pure Ti was then melted to getter any residual oxygen or nitrogen that might be present in the chamber prior to melting the raw materials. During the melting procedure, the buttons were flipped and remelted eight times to ensure chemical homogeneity before they were drop cast into a rectangular 80 mm high, 16 mm long, and 7 mm wide copper mold.

For metallographic preparations, the drop-cast ingots were cut into halves along the height (parallel to the mold filling axis) and one half was then cut perpendicular to the mold filling axis into three equal pieces, see Fig. 1a. Each piece was embedded individually in epoxy to investigate the microstructures at the top (T), middle (M), and bottom (B) of the ingots, see Fig. 1b. The embedded samples were ground down to 8 μm with SiC abrasive papers and then polished down to 1 μm with a diamond suspension. Additionally, the specimens were vibro-polished for 48 h with a colloidal Silica polishing suspension of type MasterMetTH with a particle size of 0.06 μm .

2.2. Phase characterization, microstructure and chemical composition

The crystallographic structures of the phases present in the as-cast alloys were characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using a PANalytical X'Pert Pro MRD diffractometer operating with a Cu-K α radiation source ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$). Diffraction patterns were recorded in a 2θ -range between 20° and 120° with a step size of 0.006° and an integration time of 280 s. This phase analysis was further complemented by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) to identify phases with a low volume fraction that XRD may have missed. For this purpose, thin specimens with a thickness of $\sim 200 \mu\text{m}$ were prepared from the as-cast ingots and ground down to foils with a thickness of about $\sim 75 \mu\text{m}$. Discs with a diameter of 3 mm were punched out of the foils and electron transparent regions were produced by twin jet polishing using an aqueous electrolyte consisting of 70 vol% of methanol, 20 vol% of glycerine, and 10 vol% perchloric acid at a temperature of $-20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and an applied voltage of 16 V. TEM analysis was conducted in an FEI Tecnai F20 G² S-Twin operated at 200 kV and equipped with a field emission gun (FEG), an energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDX) detector as well as a high angle annular dark-field (HAADF) detector. The average chemical composition of each identified phase was measured with EDX in

Fig. 1. Schematic drawings showing how metallographic specimens were prepared. (a) Photo of a drop-cast ingot cut into two halves (indicated by white dashed line). One half is then divided into three equal pieces as highlighted by the black dashed lines. Note that T, M and B represent the top, middle and bottom of the ingot, respectively. (b) Embedded pieces to study the microstructural evolution along the mold filling axis. (c) Schematic showing where microhardness tests were performed on the specimens. Three arrays comprising 10 indents were performed on every embedded sample.

the TEM. Using these compositions, the volume fractions of the individual phases were determined using a simple mass balance, see section D in supplementary material. Diffraction patterns of the different phases were indexed using JEMS analysis software [35].

The as-cast microstructures were examined by backscattered electron (BSE) imaging and electron backscattered diffraction (EBSD) in an FEI Quanta FEG 650 scanning electron microscope (SEM) operated at 20 kV and equipped with an EBSD detector Hikari XP camera (EDAX, AMETEK). These microstructural analyses allowed us to determine the surface area fractions of the different phases with a precision of $\pm 5\%$ and the mean prior BCC/B2 grain size (prior to the precipitation of the FCC phase and the spinodal decomposition of the BCC structure) using the linear intercept method outlined in ASTM E112–10 (mean deviation = $\pm 5\%$).

The overall chemical compositions (averaged over all phases) were measured using X-ray fluorescence analysis method (XRFA) while, as mentioned above the local chemical compositions of the phases were characterized by means of energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDX) in the TEM. In addition, the content of impurities such as O and S were determined by carrier gas hot extraction and combustion IR absorption, respectively.

Table 1

shows the nominal compositions in at.% of some of the drop-cast CCAs as well as their compositions determined using XRFA, carrier gas hot extraction and combustion IR absorption. A comparison between nominal and actual alloy compositions reveals a maximum deviation of <0.1 at.%. Additional metallic and non-metallic elements like tungsten and sulfur were also detected however their amount was below 0.01 and 0.003 at.%, respectively, and therefore their influence on the alloy microstructure and mechanical properties can be neglected. Additional chemical analyses were performed by EDX at nine locations equally spaced along the ingot's height to investigate whether the drop-cast alloys are chemically homogeneous. Note that the investigated areas for EDX analysis had the dimensions 1.2×1.5 mm² to average the chemical composition over the different phases present in the alloys. No significant variation from the targeted chemical composition could be detected along the ingot's height (see Fig. A1 of the Supplementary material). This shows that our melting procedure which comprises eight remelting steps yields as-cast ingots with a homogeneous chemical composition at the millimeter scale. In the following, Al_{13.00}Co_{21.74}Cr_{21.74}Fe_{21.74}Ni_{21.74} (in at.%) or Al_{0.6}CoCrFeNi (in molar fraction) represents the reference alloy (Al₁₃) to which different amounts of Ti, Al, and C were added to investigate their effect on the cast microstructures and mechanical properties. For simplicity, the alloys with Ti, Al, and C additions Al₁₃Co₂₁Cr₂₁Fe₂₁Ni₂₁Ti₃, Al₁₆Co₂₁Cr₂₁Fe₂₁Ni₂₁, Al_{13.00}Co_{21.69}Cr_{21.69}Fe_{21.69}Ni_{21.69}C_{0.25}, and Al_{13.00}Co_{20.94}Cr_{20.94}Fe_{20.94}Ni_{20.94}Ti₃C_{0.25} are referred to as Ti₃, Al₁₆, C_{0.25}, and Ti₃C_{0.25} in the remainder of this paper, see Table 2.

Names	Nominal compositions in at.%	Al	Co	Cr	Fe	Ni	Ti	C	S	W
Al ₁₃	Al _{13.00} Co _{21.74} Cr _{21.74} Fe _{21.74} Ni _{21.74}	12.88	21.75	21.73	21.85	21.78	–	0.005	0.005	–
Ti ₃ C _{0.25}	Al _{13.00} Co _{20.94} Cr _{20.94} Fe _{20.94} Ni _{20.94} Ti ₃ C _{0.25}	12.86	20.97	20.95	20.91	20.96	3.06	0.277	0.003	0.01

2.3. Mechanical properties

Vickers microhardness was measured using a microhardness tester KB 30BVZ (KB Prüftechnik GmbH) and a load of 10 kg following the standard test method outlined in DIN EN ISO 6507–2: 2005 D. To investigate whether the hardness is constant along the mold filling axis of the cast ingots, indents were made at nine different locations spanning the whole height of the ingots. At each location, ten indents spaced 1.1 mm apart were made as indicated in Fig. 1c.

The tensile behavior of the drop-cast alloys was characterized using cylindrical dog-bone-shaped tensile specimens (gauge length 17 mm and gauge diameter 3 mm). To prepare these tensile specimens, two rods with a diameter of 6 mm were first machined by electric discharge machining with their longitudinal axes parallel to the height of the as-cast ingots. These rods were subsequently turned on a lathe to obtain the tensile specimens. The exact locations from where the tensile specimens were taken from the cast ingots are shown in the inset of Fig. 7a. The cast alloys were tensile tested at room temperature (RT), 400 °C, and 700 °C at a strain rate of 10^{-3} s⁻¹ using a Zwick Roell Z100 Xforce machine. In the present work, two tensile specimens of a given alloy were strained to fracture at each temperature.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Composition of the CCAs

Table 1: Chemical compositions (in at.%) of some of the studied CCAs determined by X-ray fluorescence analysis method for the metallic elements, carrier gas hot extraction for oxygen, and combustion IR absorption for carbon and sulfur. The accuracy of the measured values is 0.02% and 0.005% for metallic and non-metallic elements, respectively.

3.2. Phase characterization

Fig. 2a shows an XRD pattern of the Ti₃C_{0.25} alloy which is representative of all studied CCAs. The summary of all XRD patterns for the studied CCAs can be found in Fig. B2 of supplementary material and the raw data can be found in the corresponding data in brief article. In all CCAs, two sets of diffraction peaks were identified which correspond to body-centered cubic (BCC, Space group Im-3 m) and face-centered cubic (Space group Fm-3 m) structures. Note that no other phases which may have resulted from an increase in Al content or additions of Ti and C could be detected by XRD (the detection limit is ~ 5 Vol%). Since the diffraction patterns were recorded for cast alloys, eventual superlattice reflections of ordered FCC (e.g., L1₂) and BCC (e.g., B2) phases cannot be detected

Table 2
Investigated alloy nominal compositions and corresponding names.

Nominal compositions (at.%)	Names
Al _{13.00} Co _{21.74} Cr _{21.74} Fe _{21.74} Ni _{21.74}	Al ₁₃
Al _{13.00} Co _{21.69} Cr _{21.69} Fe _{21.69} Ni _{21.69} C _{0.25}	C _{0.25}
Al _{16.00} Co _{21.00} Cr _{21.00} Fe _{21.00} Ni _{21.00}	Al ₁₆
Al _{13.00} Co _{21.00} Cr _{21.00} Fe _{21.00} Ni _{21.00} Ti _{3.00}	Ti ₃
Al _{13.00} Co _{20.94} Cr _{20.94} Fe _{20.94} Ni _{20.94} Ti _{3.00} C _{0.25}	Ti ₃ C _{0.25}

by XRD. Therefore, to investigate whether the CCAs contain ordered FCC and BCC phases and whether other phases with low volume fractions are present in the alloys, TEM characterization was performed and will be shown at the end of this section. In Fig. 2b the lattice parameters of the two crystallographic structures were determined by Rietveld analysis using the MAUD program [36] and are shown as a function of the studied alloys. The addition of C to the reference Al₁₃ alloy (C_{0.25} alloy) results in a strong increase of the FCC lattice parameter while the lattice parameter of the BCC structure is not affected. Except for the C_{0.25} alloy, all other CCAs have a similar lattice parameter of ~0.3603 nm for the FCC structure. In contrast, the lattice parameter of the BCC structure is found to change with Al and Ti additions, i.e. an addition of Al is found to decrease the lattice parameter of the BCC structure (compare reference Al₁₃ and Al₁₆ alloys in Fig. 2b) while Ti additions result in an increase of the lattice parameter (compare Ti₃ and Ti₃C_{0.25} with the reference Al₁₃ alloy). This latter result is in line with those reported by Wang et al. [37] who investigated the effect of Ti

additions on lattice parameters in two-phase FCC/ordered BCC lamellar-structured CCAs. The authors showed that Ti preferentially partitioned to the ordered BCC phase (B2) and induced an increase of the lattice parameter of the ordered BCC phase from 0.2905 nm to 0.2928 nm when the Ti-concentration increased from 0 to 12 at.%. In contrast, the lattice parameter of the FCC phase remains unaffected.

To identify whether the FCC and BCC structures determined by XRD are ordered, disordered or contain both kinds of phases, additional TEM analyses of the Ti₃C_{0.25} CCA were performed. A STEM micrograph of the microstructure is shown in Fig. 3a where three phases can be identified. From one of the large bright regions shown in Fig. 3a, a selected area diffraction pattern was recorded at the region marked with a blue circle. The corresponding diffraction pattern reveals an FCC crystallographic structure, see Fig. 3b. Another diffraction pattern from the same region (see Fig. C3 in Supplementary material) did not show the presence of superlattice reflections. Therefore, it can be concluded that the large bright regions in Fig. 3a correspond to a disordered FCC phase. Interestingly, a lamellar structure which was oriented *edge-on* (marked with a red circle) can also be observed in Fig. 3a. A diffraction pattern taken from this region is shown in Fig. 3c and could be indexed according to a BCC/B2 structure indicating a cube-on-cube orientation relationship. To identify which of the two phases in the lamellar structure is the ordered B2 phase, the B2 superlattice reflection ($\bar{1}00$) circled in green in Fig. 3c was selected to make a dark-field image. The corresponding dark field micrograph shown in Fig. 3d reveals that the bright areas in the lamellar structure in Fig. 3a exhibit a B2 structure. A comparison of Figs. 3c and d also reveals that the interfaces between the BCC and B2 phases are parallel to {100}-planes, i.e. the spots of the diffraction pattern are aligned with the BCC/B2 interfaces. This latter result suggests that this phase decomposition occurred after solidification via spinodal decomposition [21,30]. To determine the chemical composition of each phase, EDX point analysis was performed in the TEM and the results were given in Table 3. The chemical composition of the FCC phase is close to the equiatomic CrFeCoNi medium-entropy alloy with small Al and Ti concentrations. This result is in excellent agreement with the fact that the equiatomic CrFeCoNi medium entropy alloy was reported in the literature to be single-phase FCC [5,38,39]. The B2 phase is found to be strongly enriched in Ni, Al, and Ti which is consistent with the fact that NiAl and NiTi are well-known B2 intermetallics. Furthermore, the B2 phase has been reported to exist in a broad composition range, e.g. in the Al-Co-Ni [40] and Al-Fe-Ni [41] ternary phase diagrams. Finally, the disordered BCC phase is strongly enriched in Cr which is a strong BCC stabilizer and it is depleted in Ni which is known to destabilize this crystallographic structure. To summarize the TEM results, the microstructure comprises three phases: two coherent BCC (Cr-rich and Ni-poor) and B2 phases (Ni-(AlTi)-rich) which form a lamellar microstructure and large FCC regions (~CrFeCoNi). All these results are in good agreement with those reported in the literature by Wang et al. [17,25] and Choudhuri et al. [21] for the Al_xCoCrFeNi and Al_xCuCrFeNi₂ alloys, respectively.

The microstructure of the Ti₃C_{0.25} alloy was further characterized at a lower magnification using the SEM. The SE-micrograph taken at a triple point of the prior BCC/B2 grains in Fig. 4 shows similar microstructural features as those observed by TEM. In addition, three black particles can be observed: one at the triple point and two along the grain boundaries. To identify the nature of the black particles as well as the chemical partitioning between the different phases, EDX elemental maps shown around the large SE-micrograph were recorded. Four characteristic microstructural features are marked with arrows and labeled from a to d in the SE-micrograph. The EDX elemental maps clearly reveal that the black

Fig. 2. Representative X-ray diffraction pattern and lattice parameters of the identified phases in the studied CCAs. (a) X-ray diffraction pattern of the as-cast Ti₃C_{0.25} CCA. All studied alloys showed similar diffraction patterns with diffraction peaks of FCC and BCC structures. The corresponding lattice parameters of the phase are shown in (b). Here, the left red y-axis corresponds to the lattice parameters of BCC structures (BCC/B2) and the right blue y-axis shows the lattice parameters of the FCC phase.

Fig. 3. Phase analysis by TEM in the as-cast $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_{0.25}$ CCA. (a) STEM micrograph showing FCC regions indicated in blue and BCC/B2 lamellar structures highlighted with a red circle. (b) Diffraction pattern recorded from the area circled in blue in (a) showing diffraction spots of a FCC phase. (c) Diffraction pattern from the BCC/B2 lamellar region circled in red in (a). (d) Dark field image showing the B2 (bright) region. This image was recorded using the diffracted spot highlighted with a green circle in (c).

Table 3

Chemical composition in at.% of the phases comprised in the $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_{0.25}$ CCA determined by EDX point analysis in the TEM. The absolute experimental error is $\pm 2\%$ except for Ti.

Phase	Al	Co	Cr	Fe	Ni	Ti
FCC	6	22	25	26	20	1
BCC	2	17	46	27	7	1
B2	23	20	8	12	29	7

particle marked with a yellow arrow (region *a*) corresponds to a titanium carbide (TiC). The FCC phase marked at the location *b* (blue arrow) is enriched in Cr and Fe and this phase is also found to cover most the grain boundaries, Fig. 4. The B2 region *c* highlighted with a white arrow is strongly enriched in Ni, Al and Ti. This phase is also present in the two-phase B2/BCC lamellar structure *d* (indicated with a red arrow) where the BCC lamellae are strongly enriched in Cr. A comparison of the EDX elemental maps of Al and Cr in Fig. 4 shows that the B2 regions (Al-rich) exhibit a higher surface area fraction than the BCC-regions (Cr-richest regions). Finally, it is worth mentioning that Co is almost evenly distributed between the FCC, BCC and B2 phases, in good agreement with the EDX results obtained using TEM, see Table 3.

To obtain a better microstructural overview, EBSD investigations were performed in Al_{13} . The BSE-micrograph in Fig. 5a shows a triple point of the prior grains which formed right after solidification but before precipitation at lower temperatures. The region marked with a red frame in Fig. 5a was characterized by EBSD and the obtained results are presented in Figs. 5b-d. A phase map close to the triple point (Fig. 5b) reveals the presence of two phases, i.e. an FCC phase, which covers the prior grain boundaries and which is

also present inside the grains, and a BCC/B2 phase. Note that the superlattice reflections of the B2-phase could not be detected by EBSD and therefore the BCC/B2 structure was indexed according to BCC. The orientations of the FCC and BCC structures are shown in Figs. 5c and d, respectively. In these figures the colors indicate the crystal orientations relative to the surface normal (see stereographic triangle overlapping Figs. 5c and d for colour decoding). While the BCC structure exhibits the same orientation in each prior grain (see blue, purple and pink colors in Fig. 5c), the FCC phase clearly shows the presence of several variants (different colors) in the lower prior grain in Fig. 5d. These results indicate that a BCC or B2 phase formed first during solidification and the FCC phase formed through a solid-state transformation at a lower temperature. As the prior BCC/B2 grain boundaries are covered with the FCC phase, it can be concluded that grain boundaries acted as preferential nucleation sites for the heterogeneous nucleation of the FCC phase. The EBSD results also show that the FCC and BCC structures are crystallographically related through the Kurdjumov-Sachs orientation relationship in good agreement with previous reports on CCAs containing Al [20].

3.3. Microstructural evolution with Al, Ti and C additions

The microstructural evolution of the drop-cast reference Al_{13} CCA with Al, Ti and C additions is presented in Fig. 6. The left column of Fig. 6 shows low magnification BSE-images of the drop-cast microstructures where the prior grain boundaries are highlighted with black lines for clarity and high magnification BSE-micrographs are presented in the right column. The latter micrographs in Fig. 6a, c-d are centered on triple points of prior grains. The right column of Fig. 6e shows at least three triple points while Fig. 6b does not show

Fig. 4. Representative SE micrograph and elemental EDX mapping of the as-cast $Ti_3C_{0.25}$ CCA. The black particle labeled *a* located at a triple point and indicated by a yellow arrow is Ti and C rich. The FCC region *b* indicated by a blue arrow is found to be Cr and Fe rich. The B2 region *c* marked with a white arrow is Ni, Al and Ti-rich. The lamellar BCC/B2 region *d* highlighted with a red arrow comprised two phases: a B2 phase enriched in Ni, Al and Ti such as that shown in *b* and Cr-rich BCC phase.

any of them. Except for the $C_{0.25}$ alloy which shows a dendritic microstructure (dendrites: FCC, interdendritic regions: BCC/B2, Fig. 6b), all other alloys exhibit a typical Widmanstätten microstructure with two distinct contrasts at low magnification: bright plates which also cover the prior grain boundaries and dark regions between the bright plates. As shown in the last section, the bright plates are FCC while the dark regions in between exhibit BCC/B2 structures. At higher magnification, the dark regions between the plates are found to show two distinct contrasts indicating that this region comprises two different phases, e.g. pink framed inset in the

right column of Fig. 6d. These two phases correspond to B2 (darkest, rich in light elements such as Al) and BCC (less dark, Cr-rich) phases, as already shown in the previous section. Interestingly, the two phases form a modulated structure caused by spinodal decomposition (see TEM results).

The BSE-micrograph taken from the reference Al_{13} alloy in Fig. 6a reveals a coarse microstructure with a prior average grain size (d) of 108 μm , a mean thickness of FCC-plates (λ) of $\sim 1.33 \mu m$, and an FCC volume fraction of 65%. The addition of 0.25 at.% carbon to the reference Al_{13} alloy results in a much coarser microstructure

Fig. 5. EBSD analysis of the reference Al_{13} alloy. (a) BSE-micrograph centered on a prior triple point. The area marked with a red frame was analyzed by EBSD. (b) Phase map revealing FCC (red) and BCC (green) structures. Grain orientation maps of the (c) BCC and (d) FCC structures.

Fig. 6. Effect of chemical composition on cast microstructures of all studied CCAs. In the left column are low magnification BSE-micrographs of (a) reference Al_{13} , (b) $\text{C}_{0.25}$, (c) Al_{16} , (d) Ti_3 , and (e) $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_{0.25}$ alloys. From each micrograph in the left column, a corresponding high magnification image is shown in the right column. Except for the $\text{C}_{0.25}$ alloy, all microstructure shows typical Widmanstätten patterns composed of FCC plates which formed in a BCC/B2 matrix. The $\text{C}_{0.25}$ alloy shows a dendritic microstructure with FCC dendrites and BCC/B2 interdendritic regions. The volume fraction of the FCC phase, the prior grain size, d as well as the mean thickness of the FCC plates, λ are indicated at the top right and bottom left corners, respectively, of images (a-e). The pink framed inset in the right column of (d) shows the BCC/B2 interplate region while the black dots highlighted with yellow arrows in the right column of (e) are TiC particles.

with a substantial increase of the FCC volume fraction from 65% to 82% without the formation of any carbides, Fig. 6b. These results indicate that carbon atoms strongly stabilize the FCC phase where they are dissolved as interstitials which may contribute to the strength of the FCC phase [42]. An increase of the Al concentration from 13 at.% to 16 at.% in Al₁₆ results also in a coarse microstructure with a larger prior grain size ($d > 300 \mu\text{m}$, see Fig. 6c) but three times thinner FCC plates ($\lambda \sim 0.39 \mu\text{m}$) than in the reference Al₁₃ alloy, and a smaller FCC volume fraction (45% compared to 65% in the reference alloy). Interestingly alloying 3 at.% Ti to the reference Al₁₃ alloy triggers a significant microstructural refinement with a prior grain size of $55 \mu\text{m}$, a mean thickness of FCC plates of $\sim 0.47 \mu\text{m}$, and a smaller FCC volume fraction of 55% (compare Figs. 6a and -d). The decrease of the FCC volume fraction due to Al (Fig. 6c, Al₁₆) and Ti (Fig. 6d, Ti₃) additions compared to that of the reference Al₁₃ alloy (Fig. 6a, Al₁₃) can be rationalized by the fact that Ti and Al partition to the B2 phase (see Table 3) which results in an increase of its volume fraction.

The strongest refinement of the microstructure is observed when both Ti and C are alloyed to the reference Al₁₃ alloy ($d = 42 \mu\text{m}$, $\lambda \sim 0.43 \mu\text{m}$, see Fig. 6e). The addition of Ti and C results in the formation of black particles identified as TiC (see Fig. 4) which are mostly present at the prior grain boundaries and sometimes inside the prior grains. Some of these TiC-particles are highlighted with yellow arrows on the right column of Fig. 6e. TiC is a carbide with strong chemical bonds and a very negative enthalpy of formation which may form during solidification. As a result of the negative enthalpy of formation, C exclusively forms TiC particles (Fig. 6e) instead of partitioning to the FCC phase (Fig. 6b). As only 0.25 at.% of Ti is then consumed by C, we expect the FCC volume in Ti₃C_{0.25} (Fig. 6e) to be similar to that in Ti₃ (Fig. 6d) which is roughly what we find since the two FCC volume fractions are not significantly different (55% for Ti₃ versus 51% for Ti₃C_{0.25} with an experimental error estimated to $\pm 5\%$). The area fraction of TiC particles in the Ti₃C_{0.25} alloy was determined by image analysis to be 0.5%. Note that an additional alloy with 3 at.% Ti and 0.5 at.% C (see Fig. E5 in supplementary material) was also produced which resulted in a very similar microstructure and mechanical properties as the Ti₃C_{0.25} alloy (surface area fraction of TiC $\sim 1.3\%$).

When only Ti is microalloyed to the reference alloy, Ti solutes could be rejected into the melt ahead of the solid-liquid interface resulting in constitutional undercooling. This latter phenomenon destabilizes the planar solidification front which results in smaller dendrites and promotes finer cast microstructures [43,44]. Even though this phenomenon still contributes to microstructural refinement when both Ti and C are added to the reference alloy, an additional mechanism may also promote a microstructural refinement. As shown previously, TiC particles were found at grain boundaries and occasionally within the grains of the Ti₃C_{0.25} alloy. In the latter case, the TiC particles may have precipitated in the melt and act as nucleation sites for heterogeneous solidification. This mechanism is well-known to effectively reduce the grain size of metals and alloys and has been used in foundries for years [44,45].

3.4. Mechanical properties

To investigate whether the drop-cast ingots exhibit a constant hardness along their height (along the mold filling direction), microhardness measurements were performed as described in Section 2.3. Fig. 7a shows the Vickers microhardness which was measured at nine different locations along the height of the drop-cast ingots. Note that position zero represents the top of the ingot while position 80 mm is at the bottom of the ingot in contact with the Cu mold. All the alloys show similar hardness profiles along the mold filling direction of the drop-cast ingots, i.e. the hardness

remains constant between the top (position: 0 mm) and position: 65 mm from where the hardness increases gradually by 9% towards the bottom where cooling rates are higher. Since the chemical composition was found by EDX (see Fig. A1 of supplementary material) to be homogeneous, this increase in hardness cannot be attributed to a change in chemical composition, rather we think that this change is due to a slight microstructural refinement and/or a slight decrease in the volume fraction of the soft FCC phase. Further work is required to verify this hypothesis but more importantly, since the tensile specimens were taken from the part of the ingots where the hardness is constant (compare inserted photograph and hardness profiles), the tensile properties are not affected by the heterogeneity detected at the bottom of the ingots. A comparison of the hardness profiles of the five alloys shows that Al₁₆, Ti₃, Ti₃C_{0.25} alloys are harder than the reference Al₁₃ alloy while the C_{0.25} alloy is softer, see Table 4. There are three parameters that may account for the different hardnesses of the CCAs investigated in the present study. First, the relative volume fraction

Fig. 7. Hardness profiles along the mold filling axis and effect of composition on hardness. (a) Vickers hardness as a function of the position along the solidification direction of the drop-cast alloys. Note that the top of the ingot corresponds to position zero and the bottom (in contact with the copper mold) to position: 80 mm. The inserted photograph in (a) shows at which locations microhardness tests were performed and from where tensile specimens were taken. Note that the scale of the photograph corresponds to that of the x-axis. (b) Vickers microhardness versus FCC volume fraction of the investigated CCAs. The inserted micrographs in (b) show that the remnant indents cover large areas in which large surface area fractions of the different phases are present. Therefore, the hardness measurements are representative of the complex microstructures of the investigated CCAs.

of the soft and hard phases (the higher the FCC volume fraction, the softer the alloy), second, the microstructure (prior grain size, typical thickness of the FCC plates and of the BCC/B2 lamellae), and third, a change of the intrinsic properties of the different phases due to a change in composition through solid solution strengthening. In Fig. 7b, the microhardness is found to linearly decrease with increasing the volume fraction of the soft FCC phase. This linear correlation strongly suggests that the hardness is mostly affected by the FCC volume fraction and that different magnitudes of solid solution strengthening and microstructural changes between the CCAs play a minor role. The insets in Fig. 7b show a remnant indent (low magnification: black frame and high magnification: light blue frame) performed in the $C_{0.25}$ alloy where it can be seen that the hardness measurement is well averaged over the different phases present in the alloys. As all phases have to plastically deform in parallel during microindentation, it is therefore reasonable to find that the hardness correlates with the volume fraction of the soft phase.

Fig. 8 shows representative engineering stress - engineering plastic strain curves of the five investigated CCAs at (a) RT, (b) 400 °C, and (c) 700 °C. The raw data of these curves can be found in the corresponding data in brief article. For the sake of clarity, only one representative curve for each temperature is shown in Fig. 8, even though two tests per alloy and temperature were performed. Based on the tensile testing results, the five studied alloys can be divided into two groups with similar stress-strain curves. The reference Al_{13} and $C_{0.25}$ alloys belong to the first group and are rather soft and ductile, i.e. they have a yield strength σ_y of 412 ± 20 MPa and 450 ± 40 MPa, an ultimate tensile strength UTS of 932 ± 10 MPa and 908 ± 10 MPa, and a ductility of $21 \pm 1\%$ and $16 \pm 1\%$ at room temperature, respectively. The $C_{0.25}$ alloy has a comparable flow stress to the reference Al_{13} alloy even though it has a lower hardness and its microstructure is much coarser (compare Figs. 6a,b and 7). These results indicate that solid solution strengthening by carbon interstitials in $C_{0.25}$ may compensate the strengthening associated with the finer microstructure of the reference Al_{13} alloy (the thickness of the FCC plates is $\sim 1.33 \mu\text{m}$ for Al_{13} and that of FCC domains in $C_{0.25}$ is $14 \mu\text{m}$). The second group of alloys includes the Al_{16} , Ti_3 , and $Ti_3C_{0.25}$ alloys which are much stronger ($\sigma_y > 950$ MPa, $UTS > 1300$ MPa), and less ductile (ductility $< 5\%$) than those of the first group. The strongest and most brittle alloy of this group is Al_{16} followed by Ti_3 and $Ti_3C_{0.25}$, see Table 4. The $Ti_3C_{0.25}$ alloy is found to have a similar mechanical behavior as Ti_3 indicating that TiC particles do not significantly affect the tensile properties. A comparison of the two groups reveals that the additions of 3 at.% Al or 3 at.% Ti to the reference Al_{13} alloy increases its yield stress by more than a factor two while the hardness only increases by less than a factor of 1.2. In contrast to the microhardness measurements for which the hard and soft phases have to plastically deform (insets in Fig. 7b), Abuzaid et al. [31] showed that only the soft FCC phase is plastically deformed in the reference Al_{13} alloy during a compression test (the other phases are only

elastically loaded). Therefore, the role played by the FCC volume fraction is less important for compression and tension tests than for microhardness tests. We think that the factor which mostly contributes to the strength differences between the Al_{13} , Al_{16} and Ti_3 alloys during uniaxial tests is rather associated with the microstructural refinement triggered by Al and Ti additions. Indeed, these elements promote a decrease in the thickness of the FCC plates from $1.33 \mu\text{m}$ in the reference alloy to $0.39 \mu\text{m}$ for Al_{16} and $0.47 \mu\text{m}$ for Ti_3 . This microstructural refinement should result in Hall-Petch strengthening similarly to that observed in pearlitic steels [46,47] as well as as-cast nanostructured eutectoids with FCC and B2 lamellae [33]. However, further work focusing on the effect of the thickness of FCC plates on strength is still needed to confirm these results.

At 400 °C similar tensile behaviors as that obtained at RT were observed for the two groups of alloys (compare Figs. 8a and b). However, while the stress - strain curves obtained at RT for the reference Al_{13} and $C_{0.25}$ alloys were smooth, those obtained at 400 °C exhibit strong serrations which suggest that plastic flow is unstable at this temperature (see magnified stress-strain curves in the upper right corner of Fig. 8b). The occurrence of these serrations can be ascribed to two distinct mechanisms [48]: first, interstitial atoms like carbon are sufficiently mobile at elevated temperatures and can segregate at dislocation cores which are then pinned. A stress increment is then required for the dislocation to break away which is followed by a stress drop. The repetition of these two elementary processes results in a serrated flow also known as Portevin Le Chatelier effect [49]. Second, in substitutional FCC solid solutions with a medium to low stacking fault energy, the dislocations are dissociated into two Shockley partials with a stacking fault in between. At elevated temperatures, some alloying elements may diffuse and segregate at stacking faults to lower their energy. A higher stress is then needed to unpin the dislocations from the solute atoms which is then followed by a stress drop. This phenomenon known as Suzuki segregation may also result in a serrated flow [50] which was reported to occur in high- [4] and medium-entropy alloys [51]. Since serrations were observed in two alloys: $C_{0.25}$ with and Al_{13} without interstitials, the Portevin Le Chatelier effect cannot be invoked to rationalize the serrations observed in the two alloys; rather we think that Suzuki segregation is more likely to be responsible for the serrated flow observed at 400 °C (Fig. 8b).

Interestingly, the mechanical behavior at 700 °C changes sharply, see Fig. 8c. While Al_{13} , $C_{0.25}$, and Al_{16} alloys exhibit a low ductility lower than 5% at 700 °C, the Ti_3 and $Ti_3C_{0.25}$ alloys are much more ductile with a ductility between 40% and 55%. These alloys are found to work harden up to 2% plastic strain where a maximum is observed. Beyond this maximum, the alloys gradually soften until failure (see Fig. 8c). The softening behavior is also evident in the photograph of the tensile specimens after fracture (see inserted images in the upper part of Fig. 8c) where a pronounced neck can be observed in the middle of the Ti_3 specimen

Table 4

Microhardness, yield stress, ultimate tensile stress and ductility of the studied alloys. Typical experimental scatter for the hardness, yield stress, UTS , and ductility are 10%, 10%, 2%, and 10%, respectively.

Alloys	Hardness (HV10)		Yield strength, 0.2% offset (MPa)		Ultimate tensile strength, UTS (MPa)			Ductility (%)		
	RT	RT	RT	400 °C	700 °C	RT	400 °C	700 °C	RT	400 °C
Al_{13}	388	412	400	429	932	795	496	21	16	4
$C_{0.25}$	250	450	428	475	908	891	555	16	20	2
Al_{16}	459	1207	1065	605	1398	1355	679	1	4	5
Ti_3	415	1098	914	530	1415	1302	530	5	11	>55
$Ti_3C_{0.25}$	417	960	937	590	1344	1280	590	5	6	>40

Fig. 8. Representative tensile engineering stress - engineering plastic strain curves of the studied CCAs at (a) room temperature, (b) 400 °C and (c) 700 °C. The small region between 1 and 4.5% plastic strain which is marked with a grey background in (b) is magnified in its upper-right corner where it can clearly be seen that serrations (indicated by black arrows) are only observed at a testing temperature of 400 °C in the reference Al₁₃ and C_{0.25} alloys. The insets in (c) allow to compare the geometry of the tensile specimens after fracture. The Ti₃ and Ti₃C_{0.25} alloys tested at 700 °C exhibit a pronounced neck after fracture (see black circle region in the inset of (c)) while the other specimens (e.g. Al₁₆) show nearly no necking.

ruptured at 700 °C while no neck can be recognized in the Al₁₆ alloy. The origin of the pronounced neck for the Ti₃ and Ti₃C_{0.25} alloys will be discussed in the next section. The average yield stresses, UTS, and ductilities of the five alloys tested at different temperatures are listed in Table 4.

Fig. 8 shows that the yield strength of the strong group of drop-

cast CCAs (Al₁₆, Ti₃ and Ti₃C_{0.25}) slightly decreases by ~15% between RT and 400 °C and then decreases significantly by ~40% with increasing the temperature to 700 °C. This temperature dependence of the yield stress is similar to that of B2 intermetallics Fe₅₀Al₅₀ [52] and Ni_{48.9}Al_{51.1} [53] as well as eutectics Fe₃₀Ni₂₀Mn₃₅Al₁₅ with a duplex FCC/B2 microstructure [54], i.e. the yield strength of these alloys is weakly temperature-dependent between RT and $0.45 \times T_m$ (where T_m is the melting temperature) and strongly decreases at higher temperatures. As suggested by Liao and Baker [54], the plastic deformation for $T \leq 400$ °C is strongly localized in the FCC phase and dislocations are piling up against B2 domains which act as strong barriers to dislocation glide. However, as the strength of the B2 phase decreases rapidly with increasing temperature for $T > 400$ °C, dislocations can be more easily transmitted through the FCC/B2 interfaces which decreases the dislocation storage capacity of the alloy and leads to a lower strength and work hardening rate. As the work hardening strongly decreases for $T > 400$ °C, a plastic instability occurs at lower strains which results in a low maximal homogeneous elongation prior to necking, see Fig. 8c.

3.5. Fractography analysis

To get a better understanding of the mechanisms responsible for the fracture behaviors of the studied CCAs, fractography analysis was performed. Here we focus on the reference Al₁₃ and the Ti₃C_{0.25} alloys for two reasons. First, these two alloys were shown to belong to two different groups of alloys (soft and ductile for Al₁₃ and stronger and less ductile for Ti₃C_{0.25}) and to be representative of these groups. Second, a comparison between these two alloys allows us to investigate the effect of Ti and C additions on the fracture behavior. Fig. 9 presents secondary electron (SE) micrographs of fracture surfaces after tensile testing at RT for the reference Al₁₃ (a-c) and Ti₃C_{0.25} alloys (d-f). In the overview image of the fracture surface for Al₁₃ in Fig. 9a, the region highlighted with a blue frame is magnified in the lower right corner of the figure. Here, the presence of large shear bands at the surface of the specimen indicates that a large amount of plastic deformation took place before fracture. This observation is in good agreement with the relatively large ductility (~20%, Fig. 8a) of the reference Al₁₃ alloy. On the fracture surface in Fig. 9a, long shear bands spanning the fracture surface of the tensile specimen (highlighted with white dashed lines) can be observed. These features are typical for materials with coarse grain sizes in good agreement with the large prior grain size of the reference alloy ($d > 100$ μm, Fig. 6a). At higher magnification in Fig. 9b, the fracture behavior of Al₁₃ reveals mixed ductile-brittle fracture features consisting of two types of bands. The region marked with a red frame in Fig. 9b is magnified in Fig. 9c where the band highlighted with green dashed lines exhibits a high density of dimples (ductile behavior) while that marked with yellow dashed lines is flat (brittle behavior). The nature of these bands could be identified by EDX point analysis. The bands with a high density of dimples were found to be enriched in Cr, Fe, and Co which indicates that these bands delimit the ductile FCC phase while the chemical composition of the flat regions corresponds to that of the more brittle BCC/B2 phases. The fracture surface of the Ti₃C_{0.25} alloy observed at low magnification in Fig. 9d strongly differs from that of the reference Al₁₃ alloy, i.e. it is rather flat with mostly transgranular fracture (see Fig. 9d). At a higher magnification in Fig. 9e, fine quasi-cleavage facets and dimple-like structures can be observed. The region marked with a red frame in Fig. 9e is enlarged in Fig. 9f where dimples (region between green dashed lines) and flat regions with sharp edges (domain between the yellow dashed lines) could also be identified as FCC and BCC/B2 phases, respectively, by EDX point analysis. It is worth mentioning that the

Fig. 9. Representative fracture surfaces after tensile testing of (a–c) the reference Al_{13} and (d–f) $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_{0.25}$ CCAs at RT. (a) and (d) are SE micrographs showing overviews of the fracture surfaces. The inset in (a) shows shear bands along the gauge length of the tensile specimen. Except for (f) which was recorded with an in-lens detector, all images are SE micrographs. In Figs. (b) and (e) the regions highlighted with red frames are magnified in (c) and (f), respectively.

dimples in $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_{0.25}$ as well as the width of the FCC bands are much smaller than those in Al_{13} (compare the scales of Figs. 9c and f). In addition to the FCC and BCC/B2 phases, TiC particles identified by EDX point analysis and marked with dotted blue lines in Fig. 9f were found to have flat surfaces and some sharp microcracks. The larger brittleness of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_{0.25}$ compared to Al_{13} can be rationalized based on two microstructural features: (i) $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_{0.25}$ exhibits a larger volume fraction of the brittle B2 phase and (ii) its ductile FCC plates are about three times thinner than in Al_{13} alloy. For the latter case, it is indeed well-known that a decrease of grain size in single-phase FCC metals and alloys is usually accompanied by an increase of strength and a decrease of ductility which is exactly what we found when the mechanical properties as well as the microstructures of Al_{13} and $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_{0.25}$ CCAs are compared.

In both Al_{13} and $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_{0.25}$ CCAs, the fractography analysis revealed both dimpled ductile fracture surfaces (see regions highlighted with green dashed lines in Fig. 9c and f) and brittle transgranular flat surfaces (see regions highlighted with yellow dashed and blue dotted lines in Fig. 9c and f). These features are similar to those observed in multiphase $\text{Ni}_{70}\text{Al}_{20}\text{Fe}_{30}$ (FCC/L1₂ and B2) and

$\text{Fe}_{30}\text{Ni}_{20}\text{Mn}_{35}\text{Al}_{15}$ (FCC and B2) alloys as reported by Guha et al. [55] and Liao and Baker [56], respectively. In these alloys, the authors suggested that the following mechanisms lead to failure: microcracks are first nucleated within the brittle B2 phase and their growth is then arrested at the FCC/B2 interfaces. With increasing the macroscopic plastic strain, the cracks may extend into the FCC phase until the stress in front of the crack tip exceeds the fracture stress which is followed by failure (propagation of the crack throughout the whole material) [56]. Note that similar fracture surfaces were also observed after rupture at 400 °C (see Fig. F6 in Supplementary material).

At 700 °C, as the fracture surfaces were strongly oxidized (mostly Al- and Cr-oxides), additional cross-sections parallel to the tensile axis of ruptured specimens were investigated to better identify the mechanisms responsible for the fracture behavior of the CCAs. Additional EBSD analyses (not shown here) performed after rupture along the prior grain boundaries and inside the prior grains did not reveal the presence of new secondary phases which may have precipitated at 700 °C and embrittled the alloy. The left and right columns in Fig. 10 shows overview and high

magnification SE-images, respectively. The fracture surface of the reference Al₁₃ alloy in Figs. 10a,c shows mostly intergranular fracture facets. The corresponding cross-section images in Figs. 10b,d allow to confirm that the crack propagated along prior grain boundaries. In contrast to the reference Al₁₃ alloy which showed intergranular fracture at 700 °C, the fracture surface of the Ti₃C_{0.25} alloy is characterized by pronounced necking, see Figs. 10e,f. While the high magnification SE-image of the fracture surface in Fig. 10g only reveals ductile tearing, the cross-section micrographs in Fig. 10f shows the presence of several cavities. The red frame in Fig. 10f is magnified in Fig. 10h where the cavities are mostly found at prior grain boundaries. The occurrence of grain boundary cavitation at 700 °C indicates that a significant amount of deformation

is accommodated by grain boundary sliding. Indeed the cavitation results from the fact that the substitutional diffusion as well as the mobility of dislocations do not allow to fully accommodate grain boundary sliding and relieve stress concentrations at grain boundaries. It is also worth mentioning that the occurrence of grain boundary sliding at 700 °C in our alloys is consistent with the results of Schneider et al. [57] who showed that grain boundary sliding becomes effective for temperatures larger than 600 °C in single-phase FCC alloys.

The difference in ductility and fracture behavior between the CCAs at 700 °C now remains to be explained. As Al₁₃, Al₁₆ and C_{0.25} all show similar ductilities at 700 °C (<5%, Fig. 8c) and that their FCC volume fractions strongly differ, e.g. 45% for Al₁₃ and 82% for C_{0.25},

Fig. 10. Representative fracture surfaces of tensile specimens of (a-d) the reference Al₁₃ and (e-h) Ti₃C_{0.25} alloy at 700 °C. Figures (a), (c), (e), and (g) are top down views while the micrographs (b), (d), (f), and (h) are cross-section views. The red frames in (b) and (f) are magnified in (d) and (h), respectively. For more details see text.

this parameter does not have a significant effect on ductility at 700 °C. It is however fascinating that a small addition of Ti or Ti + C to the reference Al₁₃ alloy results in a strong increase of ductility at 700 °C (> 40%, Fig. 8c). As shown previously, the Ti₃ and Ti₃C_{0.25} CCAs exhibit the lowest prior grain sizes (55 μm and 42 μm, respectively) of all drop-cast alloys ($d > 100 \mu\text{m}$) and grain boundary sliding was found to be a key mechanism responsible for their large ductilities. Therefore, the high density of grain boundaries in Ti₃ and Ti₃C_{0.25} probably allows to accommodate a large amount of plastic deformation by grain boundary sliding. In contrast, grain boundary sliding is nearly ineffective in the Al₁₃, Al₁₆, and C_{0.25} alloys which exhibit a low grain boundary density and this results in a low ductility. For this reason, the ductility of the Ti and Ti + C-containing alloys is significantly greater than those of the other CCAs at 700 °C.

4. Conclusions

Aluminum, titanium and carbon were microalloyed to a reference Al_{0.6}CoCrFeNi CCA with a Widmanstätten microstructure in order to refine its microstructure in the as-cast state. The CCAs were arc melted, drop cast and they were found to have homogeneous microstructures and chemical compositions. These well-controlled parameters allowed us to study the effect of individual alloying elements as well as a combination of them on phase stability, microstructure, and mechanical properties. The results obtained in the present study can be summarized as follows:

- (1) *Al₁₃*: The Widmanstätten microstructure in the as-cast Al_{0.6}CoCrFeNi alloy (Al₁₃) form through the following steps. The melt starts solidifying with a disordered BCC phase. Two phase transformations occur upon cooling in the solid state: (i) an FCC phase precipitates at the grain boundaries of the BCC phase (ii) the remaining BCC phase undergoes a spinodal decomposition into a disordered BCC and an ordered B2 phase. The resulting Widmanstätten microstructure of as-cast Al_{0.6}CoCrFeNi is relatively coarse with a prior grain size, d of 108 μm, a mean thickness of FCC plates, λ of 1.33 μm and an FCC volume fraction of 65%.
- (2) *C_{0.25}*: When 0.25 at.% C is added to the Al_{0.6}CoCrFeNi alloy, the as-cast microstructure is characterized by a coarse dendritic microstructure. Compared to the reference alloy, the addition of C strongly stabilizes the FCC phase where it is dissolved in solid solution.
- (3) *Al₁₆, Ti₃ and Ti₃C_{0.25}*: The Widmanstätten microstructure was refined with either an addition of 3 at.% Al, Ti or 3 at.% Ti and 0.25 at.% C to the Al_{0.6}CoCrFeNi alloy. These alloying elements stabilized the ordered B2 phase with Al having the strongest effect. The addition of Ti or Ti + C was beneficial to reduce the prior grain size through constitutional undercooling from 108 μm to ~50 μm while the addition of Al was detrimental ($d > 300 \mu\text{m}$).
- (4) *Hardness*: The addition of C to the Al_{0.6}CoCrFeNi alloy was found to strongly reduce the hardness by ~34%. In contrast, the additions of Al, Ti, or Ti + C resulted in a moderate increase of the hardness by 18% for Al addition and 7% for the other two alloys. These results were found to correlate with the FCC volume fraction.
- (5) *Tensile properties at RT*: the addition of Al, Ti or Ti + C to the reference alloy strongly increased the strength by more than a factor of two but decreased the ductility from 21% to ≤5%. The yield stress correlated with the thickness of the FCC plates following a Hall-Petch type of relationship while the decreased ductility was due to the reduction of the FCC

volume fraction as well as the decreased of the FCC plate thickness.

- (6) *Tensile properties at high temperatures*: Despite a slight decrease of yield stress by ~15%, the tensile stress-strain curves at 400 °C were similar to those obtained at RT for all investigated CCAs. However, at 700 °C, the yield stress of the alloys with Al, Ti or Ti + C-additions decreased considerably by ~40%. This sharp decrease was probably due to the strong strength drop of the B2 phase observed in most B2 intermetallics in this temperature range. As a result, plastic deformation is not only confined within the FCC regions but can be transferred through the FCC/B2 interfaces.
- (7) *Fracture behavior at 700 °C*: All alloys showed similar uniform elongations at 700 °C but different ductilities. The Ti-containing alloys were ten times more ductile than the other alloys and showed grain boundary cavitation while the others exhibited transgranular fracture. The high ductilities of the Ti containing alloys were attributed to their high density of grain boundaries which allowed to accommodate a large amount of plastic deformation by grain boundary sliding.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

A. Asabre: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Validation, Visualization, Writing - original draft. **A. Kostka**: Methodology, Investigation, Software, Writing - review & editing. **O. Stryzhyboroda**: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing - review & editing. **J. Pfetzing-Micklich**: Conceptualization, Resources, Writing - review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **U. Hecht**: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing - review & editing, Funding acquisition. **G. Laplanche**: Conceptualization, Supervision, Methodology, Resources, Visualization, Writing - review & editing.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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References

- [1] B. Gludovatz, A. Hohenwarther, D. Catoor, E.H. Chang, E.P. George, R.O. Ritchie, A fracture-resistant high-entropy alloy for cryogenic applications, *Science* 345 (2014) 1153, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1254581>.
- [2] Z. Lei, X. Liu, Y. Wu, H. Wang, S. Jiang, S. Wang, X. Hui, Y. Wu, B. Gault, P. Kontis, D. Raabe, L. Gu, Q. Zhang, H. Chen, H. Wang, J. Liu, K. An, Q. Zeng, T.-G. Nieh, Z. Lu, Enhanced strength and ductility in a high-entropy alloy via ordered oxygen complexes, *Nature* 563 (2018) 546. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-018-0685-y>.
- [3] B. Cantor, I.T.H. Chang, P. Knight, A.J.B. Vincent, Microstructural development in equiatomic multicomponent alloys, *Mater. Sci. Eng. A* 375–377 (2004) 213. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2003.10.257>.
- [4] F. Otto, A. Dlouhý, C. Somsen, H. Bei, G. Eggeler, E.P. George, The influences of temperature and microstructure on the tensile properties of a CoCrFeMnNi high-entropy alloy, *Acta Mater.* 61 (2013) 5743. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2013.06.018>.
- [5] Z. Wu, H. Bei, G.M. Pharr, E.P. George, Temperature dependence of the mechanical properties of equiatomic solid solution alloys with face-centered

- cubic crystal structures, *Acta Mater.* 81 (2014) 428. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2014.08.026>.
- [6] G. Laplanche, S. Berglund, C. Reinhart, A. Kostka, F. Fox, E.P. George, Phase stability and kinetics of σ -phase precipitation in CrMnFeCoNi high-entropy alloys, *Acta Mater.* 161 (2018) 338. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2018.09.040>.
- [7] O.N. Senkov, J.M. Scott, S.V. Senkova, D.B. Miracle, C.F. Woodward, Microstructure and room temperature properties of a high-entropy TaNbHfZrTi alloy, *J. Alloys Compd.* 509 (2011) 6043. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2011.02.171>.
- [8] G. Dirras, L. Liliensten, P. Djemia, M. Laurent-Brocq, D. Tingaud, J.P. Couzinié, L. Perrière, T. Chauveau, I. Guillot, Elastic and plastic properties of as-cast equimolar TiHfZrTaNb high-entropy alloy, *Mater. Sci. Eng. A* 654 (2016) 30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2015.12.017>.
- [9] H. Döbelstein, E.L. Gurevich, E.P. George, A. Ostendorf, G. Laplanche, Laser metal deposition of a refractory TiZrNbHfTa high-entropy alloy, *Additive Manufacturing* 24 (2018) 386. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2018.10.008>.
- [10] L. Liliensten, J.-P. Couzinié, L. Perrière, A. Hocini, C. Keller, G. Dirras, I. Guillot, Study of a bcc multi-principal element alloy: tensile and simple shear properties and underlying deformation mechanisms, *Acta Mater.* 142 (2018) 131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2017.09.062>.
- [11] G. Laplanche, P. Gadaud, L. Perrière, I. Guillot, J.P. Couzinié, Temperature dependence of elastic moduli in a refractory HfNbTaTiZr high-entropy alloy, *J. Alloys Compd.* (799, 2019, 538–545). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2019.05.322>.
- [12] H. Döbelstein, E.L. Gurevich, E.P. George, A. Ostendorf, G. Laplanche, Laser metal deposition of compositionally graded TiZrNbTa refractory high-entropy alloys using elemental powder blends, *Additive Manufacturing* 25 (2019) 252. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2018.10.042>.
- [13] D. Miracle, J. Miller, O. Senkov, C. Woodward, M. Uchic, J. Tiley, Exploration and development of high entropy alloys for structural applications, *Entropy* 16 (2014) 494.
- [14] J.Y. He, W.H. Liu, H. Wang, Y. Wu, X.J. Liu, T.G. Nieh, Z.P. Lu, Effects of Al addition on structural evolution and tensile properties of the FeCoNiCrMn high-entropy alloy system, *Acta Mater.* 62 (2014) 105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2013.09.037>.
- [15] Y.-F. Kao, T.-J. Chen, S.-K. Chen, J.-W. Yeh, Microstructure and mechanical property of as-cast, -homogenized, and deformed $\text{Al}_x\text{CoCrFeNi}$ ($0 \leq x \leq 2$) high-entropy alloys, *J. Alloys Compd.* 488 (2009) 57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2009.08.090>.
- [16] C. Li, J.C. Li, M. Zhao, Q. Jiang, Effect of aluminum contents on microstructure and properties of $\text{Al}_x\text{CoCrFeNi}$ alloys, *J. Alloys Compd.* 504 (2010) S515. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2010.03.111>.
- [17] W.-R. Wang, W.-L. Wang, S.-C. Wang, Y.-C. Tsai, C.-H. Lai, J.-W. Yeh, Effects of Al addition on the microstructure and mechanical property of $\text{Al}_x\text{CoCrFeNi}$ high-entropy alloys, *Intermetallics* 26 (2012) 44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intermet.2012.03.005>.
- [18] Q. Hu, F.-c. Liu, Q.-l. Fan, H. Du, G. Liu, G.-h. Wang, Z.-t. Fan, X.-w. Liu, Effect of Al on microstructure and mechanical properties of cast CrCoNi medium-entropy alloy, *China Foundry* 15 (2018) 253. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41230-018-8031-4>.
- [19] M.P. Agustianingrum, S. Yoshida, N. Tsuji, N. Park, Effect of aluminum addition on solid solution strengthening in CoCrNi medium-entropy alloy, *J. Alloys Compd.* 781 (2019) 866. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2018.12.065>.
- [20] T. Borkar, B. Gwalani, D. Choudhuri, C.V. Mikler, C.J. Yannetta, X. Chen, R.V. Ramanujan, M.J. Styles, M.A. Gibson, R. Banerjee, A combinatorial assessment of $\text{Al}_x\text{CrCuFeNi}_2$ ($0 < x < 1.5$) complex concentrated alloys: microstructure, microhardness, and magnetic properties, *Acta Mater.* 116 (2016) 63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2016.06.025>.
- [21] D. Choudhuri, B. Gwalani, S. Gorsse, C.V. Mikler, R.V. Ramanujan, M.A. Gibson, R. Banerjee, Change in the primary solidification phase from fcc to bcc-based B2 in high entropy or complex concentrated alloys, *Scr. Mater.* 127 (2017) 186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scriptamat.2016.09.023>.
- [22] B. Gwalani, S. Gorsse, D. Choudhuri, M. Styles, Y. Zheng, R.S. Mishra, R. Banerjee, Modifying transformation pathways in high entropy alloys or complex concentrated alloys via thermo-mechanical processing, *Acta Mater.* 153 (2018) 169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2018.05.009>.
- [23] A.I. Yurkova, V.V. Cherniavsky, V. Bolbut, M. Krüger, I. Bogomol, Structure formation and mechanical properties of the high-entropy AlCuNiFeCr alloy prepared by mechanical alloying and spark plasma sintering, *J. Alloys Compd.* 786 (2019) 139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2019.01.341>.
- [24] L. Wang, F. Zhang, Z. Nie, L. Wang, F. Wang, B. Wang, S. Zhou, Y. Xue, B. Cheng, H. Lou, X. Chen, Y. Ren, D.E. Brown, V. Prakapenka, E. Greenberg, Z. Zeng, Q.S. Zeng, Abundant polymorphic transitions in the $\text{Al}_{0.6}\text{CoCrFeNi}$ high-entropy alloy, *Materials Today Physics* 8 (2019) 1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtphys.2018.12.002>.
- [25] W.-R. Wang, W.-L. Wang, J.-W. Yeh, Phases, microstructure and mechanical properties of $\text{Al}_x\text{CoCrFeNi}$ high-entropy alloys at elevated temperatures, *J. Alloys Compd.* 589 (2014) 143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2013.11.084>.
- [26] C. Zhang, F. Zhang, H. Diao, M.C. Gao, Z. Tang, J.D. Poplawsky, P.K. Liaw, Understanding phase stability of Al-Co-Cr-Fe-Ni high entropy alloys, *Mater. Des.* 109 (2016) 425. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2016.07.073>.
- [27] J. Joseph, N. Stanford, P. Hodgson, D.M. Fabijanic, Understanding the mechanical behaviour and the large strength/ductility differences between FCC and BCC $\text{Al}_x\text{CoCrFeNi}$ high entropy alloys, *J. Alloys Compd.* 726 (2017) 885. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2017.08.067>.
- [28] Y. Ma, B. Jiang, C. Li, Q. Wang, C. Dong, P.K. Liaw, F. Xu, L. Sun, The BCC/B2 morphologies in $\text{Al}_x\text{NiCoFeCr}$ high-entropy alloys, *Metals* 7 (2017) 57. <https://doi.org/10.3390/met7020057>.
- [29] J.C. Rao, H.Y. Diao, V. Ocelík, D. Vainchtein, C. Zhang, C. Kuo, Z. Tang, W. Guo, J.D. Poplawsky, Y. Zhou, P.K. Liaw, J.T.M. De Hosson, Secondary phases in $\text{Al}_x\text{CoCrFeNi}$ high-entropy alloys: An in-situ TEM heating study and thermodynamic appraisal, *Acta Mater.* 131 (2017) 206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2017.03.066>.
- [30] A. Manzoni, H. Daoud, R. Völkl, U. Glatzel, N. Wanderka, Phase separation in equiatomic AlCoCrFeNi high-entropy alloy, *Ultramicroscopy* 132 (2013) 212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultramic.2012.12.015>.
- [31] W. Abuzaid, H. Sehitoğlu, Plastic strain partitioning in dual phase $\text{Al}_{13}\text{CoCrFeNi}$ high entropy alloy, *Mater. Sci. Eng. A* 720 (2018) 238. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2018.02.044>.
- [32] G. Liu, L. Liu, X. Liu, Z. Wang, Z. Han, G. Zhang, A. Kostka, Microstructure and mechanical properties of $\text{Al}_{0.7}\text{CoCrFeNi}$ high-entropy-alloy prepared by directional solidification, *Intermetallics* 93 (2018) 93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intermet.2017.11.019>.
- [33] I. Baker, F. Meng, Lamellar coarsening in Fe28Ni18Mn33Al21 and its influence on room temperature tensile behavior, *Acta Mater.* 95 (2015) 124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2015.05.006>.
- [34] I. Baker, M. Wu, Z. Wang, Eutectic/eutectoid multi-principle component alloys: a review, *Mater. Charact.* 147 (2019) 545. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchar.2018.07.030>.
- [35] P. Stadelmann, JEMS, Electron Microscopy Software Java Version 4.6031U2017, 2017.
- [36] L. Lutterotti, S. Matthies, H. Wenk, MAUD: a friendly Java program for material analysis using diffraction, *IUCr: Newsletter of the CPD 21* (1999).
- [37] Z. Wang, M. Wu, Z. Cai, S. Chen, I. Baker, Effect of Ti content on the microstructure and mechanical behavior of (Fe36Ni18Mn33Al13)100-xTi high entropy alloys, *Intermetallics* 75 (2016) 79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intermet.2016.06.001>.
- [38] A. Gali, E.P. George, Tensile properties of high- and medium-entropy alloys, *Intermetallics* 39 (2013) 74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intermet.2013.03.018>.
- [39] G. Laplanche, P. Gadaud, C. Bärsch, K. Demtröder, C. Reinhart, J. Schreuer, E.P. George, Elastic moduli and thermal expansion coefficients of medium-entropy subsystems of the CrMnFeCoNi high-entropy alloy, *J. Alloys Compd.* 746 (2018) 244. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2018.02.251>.
- [40] Y. Wang, P. Zhou, Y. Peng, Y. Du, B. Sundman, J. Long, T. Xu, Z. Zhang, A thermodynamic description of the Al-Co-Ni system and site occupancy in Co + AlNi₃ composite binder phase, *J. Alloys Compd.* 687 (2016) 855. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2016.06.002>.
- [41] D. Liu, L. Zhang, Y. Du, Z. Jin, Simulation of atomic mobilities, diffusion coefficients and diffusion paths in bcc_A2 and bcc_B2 phases of the Al-Ni-Fe system, *J. Alloys Compd.* 634 (2015) 148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2015.01.267>.
- [42] Z. Wang, I. Baker, Interstitial strengthening of a f.c.c. FeNiMnAlCr high entropy alloy, *Mater. Lett.* 180 (2016) 153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2016.05.122>.
- [43] K. Yamanaka, M. Mori, A. Chiba, Refinement of solidification microstructures by carbon addition in biomedical Co-28Cr-9W-1Si alloys, *Mater. Lett.* 116 (2014) 82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2013.10.109>.
- [44] X.W. Liu, G. Laplanche, A. Kostka, S.G. Fries, J. Pfetzinger-Micklich, G. Liu, E.P. George, Columnar to equiaxed transition and grain refinement of cast CrCoNi medium-entropy alloy by microalloying with titanium and carbon, *J. Alloys Compd.* 775 (2019) 1068. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2018.10.187>.
- [45] X. Liu, L. Liu, G. Liu, X. Wu, D. Lu, J. Yao, W. Jiang, Z. Fan, W. Zhang, The role of carbon in grain refinement of cast CrFeCoNi high-entropy alloys, *Metall. Mater. Trans. A* 49 (2018) 2151. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11661-018-4549-8>.
- [46] B. Karlsson, G. Lindén, Plastic deformation of eutectoid steel with different cementite morphologies, *Mater. Sci. Eng.* 17 (1975) 153 ([https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-5416\(75\)90039-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-5416(75)90039-7)).
- [47] A. Marder, B. Bramfitt, The effect of morphology on the strength of pearlite, *Metall. Trans. A* 7 (1976) 365. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02642832>.
- [48] R.W.K. Honeycombe, *The Plastic Deformation of Metals*, second ed., Edward Arnold Ltd, London, 1984.
- [49] A. Portevin, F. Le Chatelier, Sur un phénomène observé lors de l'essai de traction d'alliages en cours de transformation, *Comptes Rendus de l'Académie des Sciences Paris* 176 (1923) 507.
- [50] H. Suzuki, Chemical interaction of solute atoms with dislocations, *Science reports of the Research Institutes, Tohoku University. Ser. A, Physics, chemistry and metallurgy* 4 (1952) 455.
- [51] M. Schneider, F. Werner, D. Langenkämper, C. Reinhart, G. Laplanche, Effect of temperature and texture on Hall-Petch strengthening by grain and annealing twin boundaries in the MnFeNi medium-entropy alloy, *Metals* 9 (2019) 84. <https://doi.org/10.3390/met9010084>.
- [52] I. Baker, D.J. Gaydos, Flow and fracture of Fe-Al, *Mater. Sci. Eng.* 96 (1987) 147 ([https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-5416\(87\)90549-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-5416(87)90549-0)).
- [53] A. Ball, R.E. Smallman, The deformation properties and electron microscopy studies of the intermetallic compound NiAl, *Acta Metall.* 14 (1966) 1349. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0001-6160\(66\)90251-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0001-6160(66)90251-3).
- [54] Y. Liao, I. Baker, Evolution of the microstructure and mechanical properties of

- eutectic Fe₃₀Ni₂₀Mn₃₅Al₁₅, J. Mater. Sci. 46 (2011) 2009. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-010-5197-6>.
- [55] S. Guha, P.R. Munroe, I. Baker, Room temperature deformation behavior of multiphase Ni-20at.%Al-30at.%Fe and its constituent phases, Mater. Sci. Eng. A 131 (1991) 27. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0921-5093\(91\)90341-J](https://doi.org/10.1016/0921-5093(91)90341-J).
- [56] Y. Liao, I. Baker, On the room-temperature deformation mechanisms of lamellar-structured Fe₃₀Ni₂₀Mn₃₅Al₁₅, Mater. Sci. Eng. A 528 (2011) 3998. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2011.01.089>.
- [57] M. Schneider, E.P. George, T.J. Manescau, T. Zálezák, J. Hunfeld, A. Dlouhý, G. Eggeler, G. Laplanche, Analysis of Strengthening Due to Grain Boundaries and Annealing Twin Boundaries in the CrCoNi Medium-Entropy Alloy, Int. J. Plast., accepted for publication, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijplas.2019.08.009>.